

Remote Music Tuition

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ABSTRACT

It is common to learn to play an orchestral musical instrument through one-to-one lessons with an experienced tutor. For musicians who choose to study performance at an undergraduate level and beyond, their tutor is an important part of their professional musical development. For many musicians, travel is part of their professional lives due to touring, auditioning and teaching, often overseas. This makes temporary separation of students from their tutor inevitable. A solution used by some conservatoires is teaching via video conferencing, however the challenges of using video conference for interaction and collaborative work are well documented. The Remote Music Tuition prototype was designed to enhance music tuition via video conference by providing multiple views of the student. This paper describes the system, documents observations from initial tests of the prototype and makes recommendations for future developments and further testing.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is common to learn to play an orchestral musical instrument through one-to-one lessons with an experienced tutor. A student may work with the same tutor for many years, and for those who choose to study performance at an undergraduate level and beyond, their tutor is often also their mentor, and an important part of their professional musical development. However it is not always possible to find a suitable tutor locally for a student's chosen instrument, or level of skill. The number of qualified professional tutors in any particular field is finite, but becomes more limited the more accomplished a student becomes, especially if the student chooses a less common instrument. Also musicians travel frequently as their professional lives require touring, auditioning and teaching, often overseas. Temporary separation of students from their tutor is inevitable and can happen at at crucial times in a student's development such as preparation for a milestone performance, exam or

audition. One solution is video conferencing and the technology is already available in many schools and conservatoires, especially in geographically remote areas, for example students living in remote parts of Australia [1] [2] [3].

Audiovisual quality and low latency are critical determinants of distributed musical performance [6] but in music tuition, student-tutor interaction through non-verbal communication such as use of space, and joint reference to the same physical score was found to be crucial [7]. There is extensive work available looking at the technical challenges of video conferencing such as latency, audio quality and visual resolution (for example [4] [5]). Whilst latency does make synchronous activity such as playing together extremely difficult, it has a much lower impact on music tuition than music performance. In co-present instrumental music lessons analysed alongside this work, synchronous activity such as singing, conducting, accompanying or playing together represented less than fifteen percent of total lesson time [7]. Whilst this activity is important, in instances of temporary separation a large part of the lesson could still take place via video conference.

We have developed ¹ a prototype system which enhances video conferencing equipment for the purpose of instrumental music tuition. This has been tested in collaboration with Aldeburgh Music ("Aldeburgh"), an organisation based in Suffolk which develops young musicians with the potential and ambition to become professional artists. For Aldeburgh, video conferencing represents a way to extend their global reach to musicians who would not otherwise be able to access the professional development that they need. This paper describes the Remote Music Tuition prototype, documents observations from initial tests of the system and makes recommendations for future developments and further testing. This work is important because improving the experience and availability of one-to-one learning with expert tutors, despite geographic separation, would help student-tutor pairs to sustain regular contact and allow more students to fulfil their musical potential.

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Figure 1. Remote Music Tuition prototype media and data flows.

2. THE CONCEPT OF MULTIPLE VIEWS

Video conferencing was initially developed as a tool for teleconferencing to facilitate meetings. In 1988 the failure of the technology to meet expected take-up was attributed to psychological and sociological effects, and a failure to understand how people communicate and what constitutes the feeling of “being there” [8]. The belief that technology could be developed which would replicate face-to-face interaction, simply at a distance, contained a fundamental misunderstanding about how people interact when working collaboratively to achieve a task [9]. Face-to-face interaction provides the social grounding for information exchange [10] but is not necessarily the preferred way to complete distributed work. It has long been recognised that video conferencing is not analogous to co-present experience [8, 9, 11].

Whilst video conferencing provides a visual representation, it is through a flat screen which cannot convey spatiality. The screen size available with most systems reduces the image of the student to significantly less than life-size, which reduces the efficiency of non-verbal communication such as gesture and gaze [6]. Learning a musical instrument requires manipulation of a complicated artefact in space. In a co-present lesson the tutor can choose where to look, for example at the score, the instrument, the student’s hands, the student’s feet or the position of a mouthpiece. In 1997, Heath, Luff and Sellen [12] proposed that for users of video conference “one of the obvious ways of expanding

access into another’s domain is simply to increase the number of views a participant has of the remote environment.” They asked participants to complete a collaborative design task using a video conference system devised with multiple views (The Multiple Target Video System or “MTV”). The participants’ preference for views whilst completing the task was then analysed. In the first test, only one of the views could be chosen at any time. Participants rarely selected the face-to-face option, preferring bird’s eye views of each other’s work area, or close-ups of the model for the task. When the effort to switch screens was reduced by providing all three views simultaneously on three separate monitors, the face-to-face views were used more, but only to glance at briefly between prolonged sessions of use of the other views. Gaze was more likely to be aligned to a focal point of activity, such as a shared document, individuals preferring to coordinate their actions through peripheral monitoring. During development of the prototype, we made observations of instrumental lessons using point-to-point video conference (the standard set up with one view and one camera at each end). The score and music stand became a joint reference for the participants, co-ordinating activity between student and tutor, supported by their peripheral awareness of each other. Direct mutual gaze was rarely used [7]. The Remote Music Tuition prototype applies the concept of multiple views to instrumental learning, to determine if making additional views available to the tutor to diagnose problems and assess the student’s performance, enhances distributed music tuition.

Figure 2. A tutor watching the composite screen during a test lesson.

3. THE REMOTE MUSIC TUITION SYSTEM

Music covers a larger frequency and dynamic range than speech, and the speech enhancing processing which is a feature of most video conference brands has an adverse affect on music. Polycorn have worked in partnership with the Manhattan School of Music to develop a “music mode” which suppresses speech processing as “the technologies that guarantee true music reproduction are often in conflict with the technologies developed to improve the user experience in a standard bi-directional voice call” [13]. The Remote Music Tuition prototype was designed around the Polycom model HDX6000 as a result.

The system is asymmetric, the tutor has just one camera at their location (the video conference system camera) whilst the student has three cameras, a main view provided by the video conference camera and two additional cameras (ideally small webcams which can be flexibly positioned). The visual data from the three student cameras is streamed into a separate computer through a video router and combined into a composite view using SMIL² by a visual composition engine (VCE). The Polycom system can accept two video inputs, the VCE output was provided as input B (Fig.1). Both participants could see this composite view (Fig.2) which showed the main selected view and three thumbnail representations of the views available (Fig.3). The main view could be dynamically switched through a control device, managed by the tutor, housed on a touch screen tablet computer which ran the software application through a web browser (Fig.4). The student could elect to see the main view only (Fig.5) if they preferred.

4. TESTS CARRIED OUT

Six one hour lessons using the prototype were organised across three days using students from Aldeburgh Young Musicians and visiting tutors. Two classes were scheduled per day to allow time for the resolution of any technical problems before the next sessions. The first part of each session was used to set up the camera positions (they differed in each case depending on the type of instrument)

² Synchronized Multimedia Integration Language

Figure 3. A representation of the composite view generated by the VCE.

Figure 4. A tutor operating the tablet based control device.

and take the tutor through how to use the control device. Then the participants were asked to undertake a lesson of approximately 45 minutes. The tutor had a photocopy of the student’s music.

The focus of the tests was to investigate usability of the prototype, especially the control device, and to gain an initial understanding of how the multiple views would be used in practice. As a result the prototype tests were carried out in adjacent suites at Aldeburgh, where the effect of separation could be simulated but technical support could easily be provided to both ends of the call and transmission delay, jitter and packet loss could be minimised. All audio and video signals were encoded and decoded as if for transmission over the internet, so some signal delay was present, although this was less than the delay had it also included signal transmission time. The Polycom system microphone was used for audio input at both ends, audio out being enhanced through the use of external loudspeakers. These were connected to an audio channel strip where the signal was delayed by 192ms in the tutor room to compensate for picture delay caused by processing time of the VCE. This meant that the total delay time experienced by the participants was in the order of that which would be experienced in a typical video call.

The instruments taught were harp, cello, violin, oboe,

Figure 5. A student watching the main view without the composite thumbnails.

Figure 6. Layout of the tutor room during test lessons.

piano and french horn. Some of the tutors had previous experience of teaching via video conference and some of the student-tutor pairings had worked together previously. The researcher observed from the tutor room but obtained footage from both rooms (see camera positions in Fig.6 and Fig.7) which was subsequently analysed synchronously. After the lesson participants were interviewed about their experience using the system.

5. FINDINGS

Each participant made different decisions about how they wanted to position themselves, their music and their instrument, which had to be balanced against optimising the camera views. It is recommended that documentation is drafted providing guidance to new users on how to set up the cameras at the start of a session and the views which have been found to be useful for each type of instrument. In this way, best practice found through trial and error can be permanently captured to save future users of the system valuable lesson time used for setting up.

The choices made during set up had a significant im-

Figure 7. Layout of the student room during test lessons.

pact on eye contact and therefore conversational and performing turn taking. Where the shared music stand and score were found to be the focus of co-present lessons [7] they now created a significant orientation problem for video conference lessons. In order for the student to read their music it had to be directly in front of them and roughly 30cm below eye level. However this obstructed the camera view of hands and the instrument for the tutor. Getting three useful views of the student required time and assistance from a third party, the student was not able to position the cameras alone. The most efficient set up was to arrange the main view first, and then move the two additional cameras around the student to find the best supplementary views, without losing the main view which had been agreed on originally with the tutor.

Cumbersome instruments provided a unique challenge, the harp and piano in particular. Once the harps were positioned to the tutor and student's satisfaction relative to the cameras, they were able to complete a comfortable lesson, the situation not being drastically different to that in their co-present lessons. However the tutor commented that she could not get up from her harp and walk around the student. We observed that the piano tutor had to change the angle of his upright piano so that he could see the screen without having to turn his head by ninety degrees. With an upright piano, the view of the hands is blocked by the instrument itself and the player is facing solid wood. There was not always space to place an additional stand for the desired webcam position around the instrument. Fixing a camera to the top of the piano looking down onto the keyboard was requested by the tutor, but any camera fixed to the piano itself shook whenever a vigorous section was played, making the picture hard to follow. The final additional views used provided a close up of the hands on the keys, and a view of the feet on the pedals from behind the student. However audio quality was also problematic with the pianos as their dynamic range, especially when dense passages were played, led to high levels of distortion

and clipping of the audio. This is a more general problem associated with the use of video conference for music. Further investment in a dedicated mixer to facilitate additional microphone inputs to the video conference unit and dynamic control such as compression is being considered. However this could make the student's use of dynamics less transparent for the tutor. It also introduces additional complexity for organisations considering the introduction of video conferencing for music tuition, and increases the cost of a total music tuition system which can facilitate all instrument types.

Tutors remarked that the control device was easy to use, even those who described themselves as less comfortable with technical equipment, and they all picked it up at least once during their lesson and experimented with switching views. Generally if tutors were seated, they placed the tablet on a chair alongside them so that it was accessible, indicating that they did intend to try it out. However the extent to which tutors used the device varied. Some tutors picked it up to aid diagnosis in response to hearing a specific problem in the student's playing. Others largely stayed with the main view set up at the start of the lesson, and did not frequently switch to the other views. One tutor explained during the post-lesson discussion that visually referring to the thumbnails on the screen was enough to identify that their pupil's posture was correct, so they did not feel the need to actually switch views. Tutors playing instruments which occupied both hands (such as a violin and bow) had to put something down to pick up the control device, which may have reduced use in their tests. A possible enhancement of the system could be to make it 'handsfree' through the introduction of a foot-pedal to toggle through the views with one simple button.

Tutors used the additional views in different ways, some opting for different angles of the student but others choosing more specific views, for example choosing a close-up profile of the student's mouth to look at embouchure (oboe), a close up of the student's feet to see them changing key using the pedals (harp), or angling a webcam into the bell of the french horn to see the student's hand and muting technique. Since the two additional cameras need to be flexible to accommodate this kind of request quickly, this favoured high quality webcams with a variety of clips and attachments over video cameras on tripods. Webcams tend to be smaller and less intrusive, which in a small space already containing a lot of equipment, makes the student feel less self-conscious than two larger video cameras. As a further development, one main camera plus a remote-controlled, roving, flexible additional view could be more useful than three switchable static views. Heath et al [12] found that removing barriers to switching changed the participants' use of views, so an alternative set up could be to have the three available views streamed onto three separate video screens which are available at all times during the lesson. Removing the need to switch views would help those tutors needing a handsfree solution.

5.1 Alternatives to Video Conference

During a debrief after one of the tests, the tutor, student and observers discussed the wider implications for using alternatives such as Skype, since not all students who could benefit from remote music tuition had access to an organisation with a video suite. Two of the participants in the discussion had experience of teaching using Skype. One had found the internet connection was generally not fast enough for a realistic lesson, due to reduced frame rate and visual definition. The sound quality and reduced dynamic range severely limited the relevant observations that could be made, restricting diagnosis to basics such as playing wrong notes. The quality of the microphone at the student end could not be compared to the quality of a video conference system microphone, or purpose designed studio microphone, so the sound captured was already of low quality before low bandwidth transmission degraded the audio further. However for some students, this may be all that is available to them and they will find ways to make it work for them. One member of Aldeburgh Young Musicians was using Skype to maintain the teaching relationship with her tutor in China. She started learning the Guzheng (an ancient Chinese instrument) growing up in Beijing but was unable to find suitable tuition on moving to the UK. She visits China for lessons when possible, but uses Skype to maintain the regularity of contact that is required between visits.

The discussion of how best to use limited bandwidth led to another proposed solution - using the bandwidth fully to prioritise very high quality audio with no visuals. A tutor remarked that when the visuals temporarily became unavailable during his test, he found himself focussing on the sound more and could adjust to this as a way to assess the student. In a connectivity test with two cellos prior to this study, another tutor had remarked that when visuals had been affected by jitter and packet loss, he compensated with audio "where my eyes failed me my ears helped me". Audio only lessons would free up the bandwidth requirement significantly and it may be that this could be most useful for temporary separation, where the tutor already knows the student's playing well. Audio only lessons could also be augmented by other methods such as students recording performance footage between lessons for the tutor to analyse. Alternative remote music tuition methods are worthy of further investigation.

6. FUTURE WORK

This study was the first significant test of the Remote Music Tuition prototype, and refinements both to the system and test methodology are recommended. It would be useful to ensure that clarinet students are included as participants in the design of future trials of the Remote Music Tuition prototype, since clarinets feature in the data from the co-present lesson analysis [7] so observations from the co-present and separated scenarios could be robustly compared across the same instrument type. A second study should be run with the two test sites involved being geographically separate and a more structured interview should

be carried out after each test lesson to follow up on the findings reported here. Further tests should then be carried out to compare use of the three views with the control device, to use of the views when they are provided simultaneously on three separate screens without the need to switch between them, similar to the tests carried out by Heath et al [12].

It is hoped that a further trial can be established for the prototype to be used for regular weekly lessons over a period by one consistent student-tutor pair. This would allow further evaluation of the system and provide opportunities for experimentation with use of the additional camera views. The system was always intended to record the streamed video. Initially this was to allow the tutor to rewind and review footage, live during the lesson, however discussion with users led to the conclusion that students would find it more helpful to review lessons subsequently. A recording and playback system has been designed for students to review their lesson with a choice of views, allowing then to evaluate their playing in new ways. This could also be tested during the trial.

7. CONCLUSIONS

Students and tutors were able to complete a music lesson using the prototype in all cases except for piano. The control device was easy to use but the degree of use of multiple views varied, some tutors largely retaining the main view from initial set up whilst others experimented with using the views for specific problem diagnosis. This was the first time that most tutors had used the prototype and it may be that use of the system changes with familiarity. This should be evaluated through a trial by a consistent student-tutor pair, using the system for regular weekly lessons. A repeat of the first test with revisions to the study design is also recommended. Due to the importance of the teaching relationship, and limitations of video conference to support interaction fully, it is recommended that video conference is used to manage temporary separation rather than to develop a new teaching relationship. Student-tutor pairs using remote music tuition should still meet for co-present lessons periodically. Work that requires synchronous activity such as accompanied performance can then be planned for these occasions.

By clarifying what is possible, improving through experience and sharing best practice, music organisations like Aldeburgh can make the most of technology to achieve distance learning. However there could be alternatives which could be used instead of, or as a complement to video conference for music tuition. For students who would not otherwise be able to access the tuition that they need, or are faced with temporary separation from their tutor at a crucial time, this is an encouraging outcome.

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